

EFFECT OF FORCED DEBATE COOPERATIVE LEARNING STRATEGY ON JUNIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN BUSINESS STUDIES IN LAGOS STATE

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of forced debate cooperative learning strategy on junior secondary school students' academic achievement in Business Studies in Lagos State. A quasi-experimental design of pre-test, post-test, control group was adopted. To achieve the objective of the study, one research question and one null hypothesis were highlighted and guided the study. 256 JSS3 students in their intact classes from four secondary schools in Lagos State were used as sample for the study. Business Studies Achievement Test (BSAT) was the instrument validated and used for data collection. The reliability coefficient of the BSAT was determined using KR-20 technique and the analysis yielded a coefficient of 0.75. Mean, standard deviation and t-test were the statistical measures employed for data analysis. Finding of research question showed that students taught using forced debate cooperative learning strategy performed better than their counterpart taught with the conventional method. The finding of the hypothesis revealed that there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Business Studies using forced debate cooperative learning strategy and those taught using conventional method. The study recommends among others that business teachers should employ forced debate cooperative learning strategy in the teaching of Business Studies in secondary schools and that government through the Ministry of Education should include forced debate cooperative learning strategy in the list of suggested methods for teaching Business Studies in the curriculum of junior secondary schools in Lagos State and Nigeria at large due to their immense benefits.

Keywords: Academic Achievement, Business Studies, Forced Debate

Introduction

Business Studies is a pre-vocational subject taught at junior secondary school level. It is a Business Subject that gives students the basic theoretical knowledge, abilities, and mindset required for employment or career progression in the business sector. At this educational level, the goal of the subject is to give learners a foundational understanding of the corporate world. Jimoh et al (2024) stated that the overarching goals of Business Studies as highlighted in UBE curriculum encompass equipping individuals with fundamental skills to

initiate an occupation, imparting rudimentary business skills for personal use in the present and future, preparing students for advanced training in Business Studies and establishing a correlation between knowledge and skills with the national economy. However, these purposes would be realised only if students' achievement in the subject is encouraging.

Academic achievement is crucial for achieving educational goals and measuring the standard of education. It involves excellence in academic and extracurricular activities, and indicates the achievement of short or long-term goals (Akerman,

2019). Observation and preliminary study in junior secondary school in Lagos State have shown that students' academic achievement in Business Studies falls below expectation. National Examination Council (NECO) over the years reveals that students' academic achievement in Business Studies has been quite unstable (Ediagbonya & Adebayo, 2017). The Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) results for Business Studies in 2020, 2021 and 2022 in sampled schools in Lagos State show a percentage failure of 54%, 39% and 57% respectively, indicating fluctuating performance in Business Studies in Lagos State during the years reviewed. In this wise, parents, instructors, school administrators and other stakeholders in Education have been quite concerned about this unstable achievement.

As such, several factors that could influence students' academic achievement have been identified to include academic environment, students' study habits, class size, location, gender stereotypes, parental socioeconomic background, parental support and involvement, teachers' caliber and instructional strategies among others (Ayuba, 2018; Azih & Samuel, 2019). Hence, the predominant use of conventional teaching methods for lessons delivery is seen as the main cause of students' failure (Ediagbonya & Adebayo, 2017; Boma, 2019). As a result, conventional teaching allows teachers to control their audience while students may not be inspired to participate actively in class (Jimoh et al. 2021).

Therefore, a shift from the teacher-based styles to student-focused instructional methods where students take active roles in lesson delivery while teachers control the process must be ensured to build citizens that think critically and communicate effectively. In view of this, recent researches such as Karali and Aydemir (2018), Boma (2019), Feildman (2019), Umoru and Oluwafemi (2020) have recommended the use of instructional strategies that enhance students' interest, foster their development of inquiry, thinking and problem-solving skills, as well as their

ability to work cooperatively and communicate effectively. One of such leading student-centered instructional methods is Cooperative Learning (CL). Cooperative learning is a strategy that can improve students' academic achievement, critical thinking skills, and overall well-being. It involves sharing projects, reducing stress, and promoting positive attitudes (Karali & Aydemir, 2018). Alternative cooperative learning strategies that can be used for classroom instructions as documented in literatures include STAD, Jigsaw II, TGT, Round Table Discussions, Group Investigations, Jigsaw Puzzles, Round-Robin, Think-Pair-Share, Three Minute Reviews, One-Minute Paper forced debate (Feldman, 2019). It is observed that while some of these methods have gained popularity in literatures, the effectiveness and application of forced debate have not gained much prominence in research especially in business studies aspect of business education.

Forced Debate (FD) cooperative learning strategy like the one-minute paper is an active instructional strategy that enhances learning particularly in the areas of mastering the content, developing critical thinking and oral communication skills as well as empathy (Mendo-Lázaro et al. 2020). Ikegbusi and Okeke (2022) saw Forced Debate as a method designed to teach subject related skills (like Business Studies) involving strong critical thinking and rendering informed judgments. It provides students with the opportunity to work in collaboration within a cooperative group setting, compelling them to consider alternative perspectives by mandating those that support a particular proposition earlier raised by the teacher to argue against their position instead (Centre for Teaching and Learning Queen's University (2013-14). Using this strategy, students are compelled to think about the multiple sides to an issue and interact not just with the details of a given topic but also with one another. It should be noted that this approach to learning is quite a shift in Nigeria where teaching in secondary schools is mostly teacher-centred.

Despite the fact that debate has been successfully applied in several fields including Sociology, History, Psychology, Dentistry, Nursing, Marketing, and social work, its use in the classroom later became unpopular except in competitions (Oros, 2017). However, there is a renewed interest in the use of debate as pedagogy across the world starting from 1980s premised on the philosophy that debate helps to promote critical thinking, logic, and oral communication skills. It is believed that debate can be applied from second grade in primary to undergraduate degree and mostly suitable for more autonomous, self-directed learners who can construct their own learning experiences. The persuasive nature of debate may not only require determining what to say and how to say it but also the ability to consider evidence in different ways and under different conditions which may help promote critical thinking, improve communication, enhance techniques of sourcing information, gathering, evaluating, and synthesizing data to develop arguments, foster appreciation of opposing viewpoints, and allow interactive exchange among students and teachers (Oros, 2017). These could lead to the discovery of new information, actualizing knowledge and improving students' academic achievement in Business Studies in junior secondary schools.

Although, studies on how to improve students' academic achievement in Business Studies in junior secondary schools have received significant attention locally and internationally with experts using different cooperative learning strategies. Most of the available studies on forced debate cooperative learning were conducted outside the geographical boundaries of Nigeria. There have been fewer studies that experiment the effectiveness of forced debate cooperative learning strategy on students' achievement in Business Studies particularly in Lagos State, Nigeria. Hence, the need for this study to investigate how Lagos State junior secondary school students' academic achievement in Business Studies

could be improved using forced debate cooperative learning strategy

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to determine the effects of forced debate cooperative learning strategy on junior secondary school students' academic achievement in Business Studies in Lagos State. Specifically, the study sought to determine the:

1. Difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Business Studies using forced debate cooperative learning strategy and the conventional teaching method
2. Significant effect of forced debate cooperative learning strategy on junior secondary schools students' academic achievement in Business studies in Lagos State

Research Questions

The following research question was raised and answered to guide this study:

1. Is there any difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Business Studies using forced debate cooperative learning strategy and the conventional teaching method?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean academic achievement scores of Business Studies Students taught using forced debate cooperative learning strategy and those taught using the conventional teaching method in junior secondary schools in Lagos State

Theoretical Framework

This study is hinged on social interdependence theory proposed by Johnson and Johnson in 1989. The theory suggests that individuals' outcomes are influenced by their actions and can be positive or negative. It can be differentiated from social dependence, independence, and helplessness. It suggests that group members are interdependent through common goals, and as members perceive these goals, tension arises that motivates movement

towards achieving them. This theory is relevant when individual goals are accomplished under the influence of others as in the case of cooperative learning strategies which include forced debate. Cooperative learning and social interdependence are closely related, with states of tension motivating actions towards achieving desired goals. Positive interdependence can result in promotive interaction, where individuals encourage and facilitate each other's efforts to accomplish group goals, while negative interdependence can result in oppositional interaction. No interdependence can result in any interaction, where individuals act independently without exchange, focusing solely on their own productivity and achievement.

Method

This study adopts a pretest-posttest control group, quasi-experimental design. This design is appropriate because the experiment took place in a normal school setting which may be difficult to alter to suit true experimental study. As a result, the researcher was only able to assign intact classes to groups for treatments without interrupting the class arrangement already existing in the schools. The representation of the design is presented below:

O_1	X_1	O_3
O_2	C_2	O_4

Where: O_1 O_2 -represent pre-tests observations across the group

O_3 O_4 -represent post-tests observation across the group

X_1 - represent treatment to Forced Debate (Cooperative Group 1)

C_2 - represent the control group where no treatment exists

The population of this study consists of forty-one thousand and forty (41,040) Business Studies students in public junior secondary school III (JSS 3) from one hundred and seventy-one (171) public junior secondary schools in Lagos State. The sample size for

this study consists of two hundred and fifty-six (256) JSS 3 Business Studies students in four (4) intact classes from two education districts in Lagos State. The sample comprised 149 Business Studies students from Education Districts III and 107 Business Studies students from Education District II. The sample was selected using stratified random sampling techniques through a multi-stage sampling process. Business Studies Achievement Test (BSAT) is the instrument used for collection. BSAT is a sixty (60) multiple choice test items which covers topics from the JSS 3 syllabus. The reliability of the instrument was ensured through Kuder Richardson (KR-20) Reliability technique. It was trial tested on forty-five (45) Business Studies junior secondary school III (JSS 3) students of Imota Community Junior High School, Imota; Ibeju-Lekki Junior High School, Ibeju and Ojota Junior Secondary School, Ojota in Lagos State, which were outside the sample of the study. The data gathered were analysed and the result yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.75 indicating that the instruments was reliable for the study. Prior the commencement of the treatment and immediately after the initial visitation and training of research assistants; a pre-test was administered to determine the students' initial group difference or equivalence. Thereafter, a six-week treatment commenced in the experimental group where the JSS 3 students in Army Children Junior High School, Epe and Igboye Community Junior Secondary School, Igboye were taught using the Forced Debate strategy while those in Oriwu Junior Model College, Ikorodu and Igbokuta Junior Model College Igbokuta were left with the conventional teaching strategy. The data obtained from the pre-test and post-test were analysed using the descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while the inferential statistics of t-test was used for the test of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

A) Answering the Research Questions

Research Question One: What is the difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Business Studies using the Forced Debate

cooperative learning strategy and the conventional teaching method?

Table 1:

Mean Achievement Score and Standard Deviation of Students Taught Business Studies with Forced Debate and Conventional Teaching Method

Treatment Strategies	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
		Mean	Std. Dev	Mean	Std. Dev	
Forced Debate Strategy	149	21.32	5.14	45.64	7.86	24.32
Conventional Teaching Method	107	21.49	5.45	23.78	5.43	2.29

Result of analysis in Table 4.2 shows a pretest mean achievement score of 21.32 and a posttest mean achievement score of 45.64 for students exposed to Business Studies instruction using FD cooperative learning strategy. The result also shows a pretest mean achievement score of 21.49 and posttest mean achievement score of 23.78 for students exposed to Business Studies instruction using the conventional teaching method. A comparison of the two sets of scores shows a mean gain of 24.32 in the posttest achievement score of students exposed to Business Studies instruction using FD and 2.29 for students exposed to Business Studies instruction using

Table 2:

conventional teaching method. Since the mean gain of experimental group two (FD) is greater than the mean gain of control group (conventional method), it means that students taught using Forced Debate strategy had a higher achievement score than those taught using conventional teaching strategy.

B) Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of Business Studies Students taught using forced debate cooperative learning strategy and those taught using the conventional teaching method in junior secondary schools in Lagos State

T-test Statistics showing Significant Difference between the Academic Achievements of Students Taught using Forced Debate Cooperative Learning Strategy and those Taught using the Conventional Teaching Method

Strategies	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Df	t-value	Sig. (2-tailed)	Remark
Forced Debate Strategy	149	45.64	7.86	254	24.82	0.00	Significant
Conventional Method	107	23.78	5.43				

Result in Table 2 shows a t-value of 21.87 and a significant value of 0.00. Since the computed significant (p-value) is less than the Alpha level of significance ($p < 0.05$), the null hypothesis of no significant difference between mean academic

achievement scores of students taught forced debate cooperative learning strategy and those taught using the conventional teaching method is hereby rejected. This means that there is a significant difference between mean academic achievement scores of

Business Studies Students taught using forced debate cooperative learning strategy and those taught using the conventional teaching method in junior secondary schools in Lagos State.

Discussion of Findings

The study found that students exposed to Business Studies instruction using Forced Debate performed better than those taught with conventional teaching method. This result could be due to the potency of FD in ensuring active learning through constructive arguments that bring about mastery of Business Studies contents, developing critical thinking as well as oral communication which helps in boosting students understanding of the concepts in Business Studies. Like other cooperative strategy, FD provides business students with the opportunity to work in collaboration within group setting. By compelling students to argue against their position, they have considerable number of alternative perspectives that broaden their understanding on every aspect of Business Studies which translate into better academic achievement than the conventional teaching method. This finding corroborates the report of Ina Timbu (2023) that debate is an appropriate technique for improving students speaking skills. It aligns with the finding of Amani and Ali (2021) that participants enjoy and learn from debate experiences which improve their academic achievement and communicative skill than their counterparts in conventional teaching environment. Similarly, the report of Ikegbusi and Okeke (2022) that students in cooperative learning class perform better than those in the conventional method group aligns with the result of this study. Azlyn et al. (2018) reported that FD brings out the competence and confidence in students sharpening their interpretation, analytical and inferential skills which helps them gain better than their counterparts. The report of Moomala et al. (2015) that debate boost the critical thinking, enhances students' overall openmindedness, inquisitiveness, analyticity, systematicity and

confidence among Malaysian second language learners.

It was also found that a significant difference exists between mean academic achievement scores of Business Studies Students taught using forced debate cooperative learning strategy and those taught using conventional teaching method. This result is connected to the fact that forced debate strategy encourages critical thinking provides diverse learning opportunities and contributes to high academic achievement. This method offer advantages in achieving and retaining learning contents. This finding is consistent with the reports of Azlyn et al. (2018) that forced debate brings out the competence and confidence in students especially using their interpretation skills, analytical skills, and inferential skills which helps them to gain better understanding of concepts than their counterparts, align with this result. Also, it aligns with the finding of Eze and Lasisi (2018) that students taught Basic Technology using cooperative learning perform better with higher posttest scores than those taught using the conventional method. Similarly, Ikegbusi and Okeke (2022) that there is a significant effect of treatment with cooperative learning on students' academic achievement. It also agrees with the report of Kaymak et al (2021) that treatment with CL strategies has significant positive effect on students Mathematics achievement. The finding of Angrolia and Musa (2020) that the rate of CL effectiveness is high in improving achievement in Literature in English among secondary school students in Dodoma city, also aligns with this result. This finding contradicts the report of Tri (2017) that the use of FD without adequate preparation brought about poor control of emotions, poor expressions and poor achievement in teaching and learning speaking. It also negates the report of Brown (2015) that majority of the students exposed to debate (fourteen out of the sixteen) prefer other teaching strategies to debate because it does not help to improve them in learning.

Conclusion

This study examined the effect of forced debate cooperative learning strategy on junior secondary school students' academic achievement in business studies in Lagos State and it was concluded from the results that the use of forced debate cooperative learning strategy is more effective in enhancing students' academic achievement in Business Studies than the conventional method because students taught using the strategy performed better than their counterparts. This is because the strategy as one of the cooperative learning structures encourages critical thinking, provides flexibility for active learning, offer diverse learning opportunities and generated higher achievement scores. In this vein, this study has been an eye opener to the fact that where appropriate teaching methods are employed in teaching Business Studies in junior secondary schools; the academic achievement of students would be greatly improved which would lead to the realization of the overall objectives of the subject. Therefore, this study has been able to contribute to knowledge by exposing the potential benefits of and procedure for the use of forced debate cooperative learning strategy.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

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1. Business studies teachers should employ the use of forced debate cooperative learning strategy for teaching of business studies in secondary schools in Lagos and Nigeria at large.
 2. Government through the Ministry of Education should include forced debate cooperative learning strategy in the list of suggested methods in the curriculum of junior secondary schools for Business Studies' instruction in Nigeria.
 3. The state government should regularly organize and sponsor the Business Studies teachers for periodic training that will expose them to the practical application of forced debate cooperative techniques in teaching Business Studies in the junior secondary schools for better academic achievement.
 4. Business Studies teachers should ensure proper grouping, monitoring and supervision of students during the implementation of forced debate to obtain its full benefits during Business Studies instructions since the use of the strategy requires proper planning and coordination.
 5. Administrators of junior secondary schools should create enabling work environment for utilizing forced debate cooperative learning strategy by allocating sufficient time to Business Studies class on the school time table to accommodate the use of the strategy
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